

Analysis of the Relationship Between Trade Openness and Technology Innovation in Enhancing Economic Growth in Multinational Companies

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ABSTRACT

Since entering the Millennium era, world developments in the field of technology have been running at high acceleration. Several countries that were once well aligned in the economic and industrial fields are now lagging behind other countries. Rapid progress is due to very good mastery of technology so that it is able to compete globally. Mastering technology is an integral part of qualified human resource capabilities which are strongly influenced by education and economic capacity as a support. To support the necessary attractiveness support and internalization of work attitudes in encouraging the nation's competitiveness. Technological innovation plays a very important role in capturing trade for economic growth in multinational companies. Technological innovation can improve operational efficiency, improve product and service quality, encourage new product and service innovations, and facilitate access to global markets. Therefore, it is important for multinational companies to continue to invest in technological innovation in order to maintain their competitiveness in the global market.

INTRODUCTION

Trade openness refers to a company's ability to engage in international trade with other countries, while technological innovation involves the development and application of new technologies to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of a company's operations. Technological innovation involves the development and application of new technologies to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of a company's operations. Trade openness can provide significant benefits for companies in increasing their economic growth. By engaging in international trade, companies can expand their markets, increase market share, and access new customers in other countries. Technological innovation also plays an important role in increasing the company's economic growth. By developing and implementing new technologies, companies can increase productivity, improve product quality and services, and reduce production costs. Technological innovation can also help companies face increased global competition by creating a competitive advantage through developing new products or upgrading existing technologies. Economic growth in multinational companies is a process of increasing the economic value of these companies in all countries in which they operate.

Multinational companies can expand their market by expanding their market share in various countries. This can be done through opening new branches, acquiring local companies, or cooperating with local partners. By expanding the market, companies can reach more consumers and increase their income. Product innovation and efficiency improvements: Multinational companies often have access to the latest technology and sufficient resources to innovate products. By innovating, companies can create products that are more attractive to consumers and increase their competitiveness. In addition, companies can also improve their operational efficiency by implementing more efficient technology and production processes.

Multinational companies can increase their investment in different countries to increase their production capacity. This can be done by building new factories, expanding existing production facilities, or improving their production technology. By increasing production, companies can meet the higher demand and increase their income. Multinational companies can also diversify their business by expanding into various industrial sectors. This can be done by introducing a new product or acquiring a company operating in a different industry. Business diversification can help companies reduce risk and expand their sources of income. The benefits of economic growth for multinational corporations include increased revenues and profits, increased competitiveness, access to new markets, and advantages of scale. However, this economic growth can also pose challenges such as changes in market conditions, tighter competition, and different regulations in each country.

The relationship between trade openness and technological innovation is very close. Trade openness can encourage companies to innovate to staybersaing on the international market. When companies are open to international competition, they may be motivated to develop and implement new technological innovations in order to compete with other global

companies. Conversely, technological innovation can also strengthen trade capture, as innovative companies tend to have more attractive products and services to offer in international markets. The importance of finding trade and technological innovation in increasing the economic growth of companies, analysis of the relationship between the two becomes a matter of relevance. By understanding how hidden trade and technology influence each other, companies can develop appropriate strategies for their improvement and sustainability. This analysis can involve collecting and analyzing data on the level of trade involvement, technological innovation, economic growth, and other factors that might influence the relationship between the two.

Analysis of the relationship between trade setups and technological innovation is an important concept in the context of corporate economic growth. Through a better understanding of how these two factors intertwineconnected, achieving higher economic growth. The company's current business activities are no longer limited to domestic activities, but also involve international trade activities and investment abroad. This is related to globalization and trade liberalization which have opened global markets for companies to export their products and invest overseas. The decision to export and take advantage of the global market is not an easy one, because companies must consider various factors including the ever-changing global economic conditions and increasingly fierce competition. In addition, many companies are also considering outsourcing in order to obtain higher profits, but there are also great risks and disadvantages in implementing the outsourcing strategy. In addition, the activities of multinational companies operating in various countries are also an important topic because they have an impact on the global economy and the environment in the countries where they operate.

The benefits of social media as a marketing tool in the world of education in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 is a very appropriate choice because it is increasingly accessible to various groups. (Neneng Nurmalasari and Masitoh, 2020). The main objective of the company in making decisions to export, outsource, and operate as a multinational company is to increase the profit and growth of the company, as well as gain from the difference in price or production costs in the country of origin and in the global market. Indonesia's exports in January 2022 again recorded impressive performance after showing growth of 25.31% (yoy), bringing January 2022 exports to US\$19.16 billion. The main factor that maintained this positive performance was Indonesia's mainstay commodity exports which remained solid amid the ongoing trend of rising prices in several commodities, especially the commodity price of kernel oil which increased by 17.96% (mtm), nickel increased by 11.69% (mtm), and aluminum increased by 11.52% (mtm). The downstream of these commodities is also the main determinant of the increase in the added value of exports in January 2022. (ekon, go.id).

Meanwhile, the presence of multinational companies in foreign countries aims to take advantage of market potential in these countries to diversify products and increase investment diversification so as to increase opportunities for growth and development. Market potential is anything that has the

potential to provide benefits for the company. (Sembiring R and Harahap N, 2022). Economic growth in multinational companies is a process of increasing the economic value of these companies in all countries in which they operate. Multinational companies can expand their market by expanding their market share in various countries. This can be done through opening new branches, acquiring local companies, or cooperating with local partners. By expanding the market, companies can reach more consumers and increase their income. Product innovation and efficiency improvements: Multinational companies often have access to the latest technology and sufficient resources to innovate products. By innovating, companies can create products that are more attractive to consumers and increase their competitiveness. In addition, companies can also improve their operational efficiency by implementing more efficient technology and production processes.

Multinational companies can increase their investment in different countries to increase their production capacity. This can be done by building new factories, expanding existing production facilities, or improving their production technology. By increasing production, companies can meet the higher demand and increase their income. Business diversification: Multinational companies can also diversify their business by expanding into different industrial sectors. This can be done by introducing a new product or acquiring a company operating in a different industry. Business diversification can help companies reduce risk and expand their sources of income. The benefits of economic growth for multinational corporations include increased revenues and profits, increased competitiveness, access to new markets, and advantages of scale. However, this economic growth can also pose challenges such as changes in market conditions, tighter competition, and different regulations in each country.

The company's goals are not only profit-oriented, but must also consider the impact on the environment and social aspects in the countries where it operates. Therefore, companies must also consider broader goals, such as providing social benefits to local communities or complying with environmental regulations in force in the country. The challenge is how companies can consider global economic factors in making decisions to export products. And implementing corporate strategy in taking advantage of global market opportunities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Export

Keynesian theory states that exports are one of the constituent components of national income for an open economy (four-sector economy) in which the government is involved (Fauziah S and Nugroho 2022). In export decisions, companies will consider factors such as market potential, profit potential, market risk, export-import regulations and policies from the government, as well as the company's ability to meet international market needs. Export decisions depend on many factors, including industry structure, available resources, managerial capabilities, and perceptions of risks and opportunities in international markets.

Multinational Companies

Multinational companies or often abbreviated as MNC (Multinational Corporation) are companies that operate in several countries through subsidiaries or affiliates. Multinational companies usually have cross-country business, where companies will consider various factors such as profits, risks, production costs, market potential, and government regulations in deciding to start or expand their business in other countries. Multinational companies may also choose to undertake acquisitions or mergers with other companies in other countries as part of their global expansion. Multinational corporations play an important role in global trade and the global economy, and are often involved in global social and environmental issues.

Market Share

Market share or market share is the market controlled by certain companies, it can also be a comparison of the sales results of certain companies with the sales results of competitors (Wati A, et al, 2023). Market share can be measured in various ways, such as the percentage of product sales in one industry or the percentage of product users in one geographic area. It is important for businesses to understand their market share and compete for market share in an effective way to achieve growth and success. Market share is often used by companies to measure how successful they are in entering and staying in the market. Market share can be calculated by dividing a company's sales by total sales in that market, then multiplying the result by 100 to get a percentage. For example, if a company's sales are 50 million and the total sales in the market are 250 million, then its market share is 20% ($50/250 \times 100$).

Market share is important for a company because it can provide information about its position in the market and how well the company competes with its competitors. Companies with a large market share tend to have a competitive advantage and the ability to control prices and competition in that market. In addition, market share can also be used to measure market growth and potential in the future. The market share of a company, such as product or service quality, price, distribution, marketing, and competitiveness. Companies need to understand their market and customers well in order to build an effective strategy to increase their market share.

Technological Innovation

Technological innovation is the use of e-commerce technology as an alternative solution in innovating strategies to make the existing business processes sustainable (Parinda S et al, 2023). Technological innovation is the process of developing and implementing new ideas to create new solutions, products or services using technology. Technological innovation is carried out to improve efficiency, quality, and user satisfaction in various fields, such as communication, transportation, health, energy, and others. Technological innovation involves research and development (R&D) to discover and develop new ideas, as well as the application of existing or new technologies to create better solutions. Technological innovation can also trigger economic growth,

create new jobs, and provide business and investment opportunities. Therefore, technological innovation is very important to continue to be developed and supported by the government, research institutions, companies and the wider community.

Competition

Competitors are companies that sell or produce goods and services that are similar or the same as the products offered by the company (Yuniarsih C et al, 2023). Competition can occur in many areas, such as product price, product quality, customer service, product innovation, and others. Competitors in the market can be a threat to the business if they are not able to compete well and achieve competitive advantage. Therefore, a business must conduct market and customer analysis before making the right strategy to compete with its competitors.

Supply Chain or supply chain

Supply chain management is the management of activities in order to obtain raw materials into goods in process or semi-finished goods and finished goods and then send these products to consumers through a distribution system. (Warella S et al, 2021). Supply Chain is a line that is related to the process of production and distribution of a product from raw materials to the final consumer. Supply chain includes all processes involved in purchasing, raw material processing, production, packaging, and selling of products. to create efficiency and effectiveness in the processes involved, as well as minimize the cost and time required in each stage.

Improved Efficiency

Every activity that will be carried out in achieving the target requires efficiency in carrying out a job so that the target is achieved according to what has been planned properly (Sufri N et al, 2021).

Increased efficiency can be achieved by:

1. Increase the effectiveness of the use of available resources.
2. Reduce unnecessary scales and repetition of tasks.
3. Improving work processes so that they are more effective and efficient.
4. Increasing the use of more modern technology and information systems.
5. Optimize the management and selection of the right personnel.
6. Provide proper motivation and training to employees.

By increasing efficiency, companies will be able to save costs and increase profits. It will also make the company more competitive in an increasingly tight market. Therefore, efficiency is an important factor that must be considered in the management of a company or organization.

Figure 1. Management of a Company or Organization

METHODOLOGY

This research method uses applied research methods with the aim of applying, testing, and evaluating the ability of a theory and providing some descriptions of solutions to problems related to economic growth in multinational companies to develop or improve existing products, processes, or technologies. The results of applied research can be used directly by society or industry to improve the efficiency or quality of the products or services they offer. This research uses scientific methods that involve experiments or testing in the field.

RESULTS

Trade openness also has a significant impact on a company's ability to innovate in technology. Therefore, analyzing the relationship between trade openness and technological innovation is important in understanding how economic growth can be increased. Trade openness includes economic policies that allow companies to interact with global markets. In the context of technological innovation, trade openness allows companies to have access to various resources and knowledge from international markets, adopt new technologies that can improve efficiency and competitiveness. With trade openness, companies can also access larger markets. improve the quality of existing products. Trade openness can encourage companies to increase technological innovation activities as an effort to increase economic growth.

The activities of multinational corporations have a major impact on the global economy. Multinational companies can bring investment and technology

to the countries in which they operate, which can enhance the country's economic growth. However, the presence of multinational companies can also lead to stiff competition for local companies and can increase social inequality because they sometimes discriminate against workers' rights. Multinational corporations can also influence regulations and policies in the countries in which they operate, which can affect human rights and the environment. Effective marketing strategy in the global market, innovating in the products or services offered and optimizing the supply chain. In addition, companies must know and take advantage of existing international trade policies and establish partnerships with other companies to expand their network and strengthen their client base. In order to maintain a competitive advantage in the global market, companies must also pay close attention to product quality, production costs, and innovation.

There are several links between export decisions, the global economy, outsourcing, and multinational companies, including:

1. Export decisions can affect the global economy. When companies decide to export products or services to international markets, it can increase the exchange of goods and services between countries, increase competition, and create new opportunities for economic growth.
2. Outsourcing can impact multinational corporations and the state of the global economy. By moving production to other countries, multinational companies can optimize costs and increase their profits, but this can also lead to trade imbalances and unemployment in the companies' home countries. In addition, outsourcing can also affect the state of the global economy because multinational companies consider the economic and political conditions of the country.
3. Multinational companies play an important role in export and outsourcing decisions. Multinational companies have complex business networks and can take advantage of available resources, both in their home countries and investment destination countries. In exporting and outsourcing decisions, multinational companies consider global market conditions, government regulations, and other factors in the investment destination country.

The decisions of exports, outsourcing and multinational companies are intertwined and greatly affect the global economy. Companies must carefully consider the factors associated with this decision to ensure business success in global markets and provide benefits to the global economy as a whole. The main consideration in deciding whether to export/globalize, outsource, or multinational operations is market potential. If companies see an attractive opportunity in a global market, outsource, or are a multinational company, they may decide to expand their business overseas. Company decisions in exporting/globalization, outsourcing, and multinational operations. If production costs are lower abroad, firms may decide to move their production to another country to reduce costs and increase profits.

Improved Efficiency

Improved efficiency is an important factor influencing company decisions in exporting/globalization, outsourcing, and multinational operations. Companies may take steps to improve their operational efficiency by seeking business partners who can help them improve production efficiency and reduce operating costs. Government Regulations: Government regulations and regulations applied in different countries can affect a company's decision to export/globalize, outsource, and multinational operations. Companies must consider the regulations and policies of each country before entering the global market.

Technology and Innovation

Technology and innovation are important factors influencing company decisions to export/globalize, outsource, and multinational operations. Companies may seek overseas business partners for the latest technologies and innovations that can help them increase efficiency and reduce production costs.

Competition

Competition in global markets is an important factor in a company's decision to export/globalize, outsource, and multinational operations. Companies must consider competition in the global market and choose the right strategy to compete with other competitors.

Supply Chain

The supply chain is an important factor influencing company decisions in exporting/globalization, outsourcing, and multinational operations. Companies must consider the supply chain in the destination country before deciding to enter global markets or outsource or multinational operations.

DISCUSSION

In analyzing the relationship between trade openness and technological innovation of quality human resources, and the investment required in economic growth, the application of it to multinational companies. in research and development. All these factors are interrelated and contribute to creating a conducive environment for companies to innovate and grow. In order to increase the company's economic growth, it is important for the government and companies to pay attention to trade and technological innovation as interrelated factors. Implementing open trade policies, increasing access to global resources and knowledge, and investing in research and development can all be important steps in driving technological innovation and corporate economic growth.

Companies can consider global economic factors in making decisions to export products by conducting thorough market research by considering currency fluctuations, trade tariffs, and logistics costs as global economic factors that can affect profits from product exports. Through a deep understanding of these factors, companies can make better decisions in entering the global market. The advantages of outsourcing include reduced production costs as

companies can utilize cheaper labor in certain countries. Outsourcing can also increase production efficiency because companies can focus on their core activities and delegate other work. However, loss of outsourcing can occur if the quality of work from the contractor is lower than expected or if problems occur in the delivery of goods. In addition, outsourcing can also cause problems in public acceptance of the company if there is a contract that has a negative social and economic impact on the contractor.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Technological innovation plays a very important role in trade openness for economic growth in multinational companies. Here are some reasons why technological innovation is important in this regard:

Improve efficiency

Technological innovations enable multinational companies to increase their operational efficiency. By implementing the latest technology, companies can automate processes, reduce production costs and increase productivity. Quality improvement: Technological innovations also help multinational companies improve the quality of their products and services. Through intensive research and development, companies can produce more innovative products, which can transform markets and create new opportunities for trade. Thanks to technological innovation, companies can create competitive advantages that set them apart from competitors, spur economic growth and open up new opportunities in international trade.

Increasing access to global markets: Technological innovations, especially in terms of communication and transportation, have reduced geographical barriers in international trade. Multinational companies can easily communicate with their business partners around the world and send products to global markets quickly and efficiently. Technological innovation has also opened doors for small and medium businesses to engage in international trade. With the help of the right technology, small companies can access global markets and compete with big companies. Companies must consider global economic factors in making decisions to export products by conducting in-depth market research. In outsourcing, the company must take into account the advantages and disadvantages that may occur due to the use of contractor services.

The activities of multinational companies have a major impact on the global economy, so it is necessary to consider the social, environmental and regulatory impacts in the countries where they operate. Meanwhile, to take advantage of global market opportunities and maintain competitive advantage, companies must develop effective strategies in marketing, product innovation, and partnerships to expand networks and reduce production costs.

FURTHER STUDY

Research on relationship analysis finds trade and technological innovation in increasing economic growth in multinational companies can provide important insights for modern companies that want to expand their

markets and increase their competitiveness in global markets. This research will help companies and governments to plan the necessary policies to stimulate growth and technological innovation in improving overall economic performance. Several indicators and variables that will be considered in this study include market access, foreign investment, human resources and technology, research and development, and product innovations produced.

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